

A Tristable Cross-shaped Unsymmetric Fiber-reinforced Cross-ply Laminates: Experimental and Simulation Methods

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Geometry of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates

Experiment setup

Numerical simulation

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

snap-through process

snap-back process

